

TITLE: REALM OF QUANTUM NUMBERS

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Abstract:

This thesis presents a comprehensive method for deriving all quantum numbers associated with quantum systems by utilizing a set of mathematical equations. Quantum numbers, which include the principal, azimuthal, magnetic, and spin quantum numbers, are crucial for describing the properties of particles in quantum mechanics. By applying a systematic approach, this research develops equations that accurately determine these quantum numbers for various quantum states. The study's findings contribute to a deeper understanding of quantum mechanics and provide a robust framework for solving quantum systems. This work has implications for both theoretical studies and practical applications in quantum physics, offering new insights into the quantization of physical properties in microscopic systems.

Introduction to Four Quantum Numbers:

In the realm of quantum mechanics, a fundamental theory governing the behavior of particles at the smallest scales, understanding the electronic structure of atoms is essential. Four quantum numbers arise as indispensable descriptors in characterizing the complex electronic configurations within atoms. These

quantum numbers provide a framework for delineating the distribution of electrons around the nucleus, shedding light on the intricate properties and behaviors of matter.

The electronic structure of an atom is determined by its electrons, which are characterized by four quantum numbers: the principal quantum number (n), the azimuthal quantum number (ℓ), the magnetic quantum number (m_ℓ), and the spin quantum number (m_s). These quantum numbers arise from solving the Schrödinger equation for the hydrogen atom, yielding solutions that incorporate both the particle-like and wave-like nature of electrons.

Equations for Four Quantum Numbers:

1. Principal Quantum Number (n):

The principal quantum number determines the main energy level or shell in which an electron resides. It quantizes the electron's energy and distance from the nucleus. Its values are positive integers (1, 2, 3, ...)

$$n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$$

2. Azimuthal Quantum Number (ℓ):

The azimuthal quantum number specifies the subshell and the angular momentum of an electron within a given energy level. It defines the shape of the electron cloud. Its values range from 0 to $(n-1)$, corresponding to s, p, d, f orbitals, respectively.

$$0 \leq \ell \leq n-1$$

3. Magnetic Quantum Number (m_ℓ):

The magnetic quantum number designates the specific orientation of an electron's orbital within a subshell. It takes integer values between $-\ell$ and ℓ , including zero. Each value represents a spatial orientation of the orbital in relation to an external magnetic field.

$$-\ell \leq m_{\ell} \leq +\ell$$

4. Spin Quantum Number (m_s):

The spin quantum number describes the intrinsic angular momentum, or "spin," of an electron. It denotes the electron's magnetic moment due to its spin. It can take on two values: $+\frac{1}{2}$ (spin-up) and $-\frac{1}{2}$ (spin-down).

$$m_s = +\frac{1}{2} \text{ or } -\frac{1}{2}$$

Together, these four quantum numbers provide a comprehensive description of an electron's location, energy, orientation, and intrinsic property within an atom. They form the basis for understanding atomic structure, chemical bonding, and the periodic properties result, these quantum numbers are integral to the foundation of modern chemistry and physics, bridging the gap between the macroscopic world we perceive and the intricate quantum realm that governs the behavior of matter at its most fundamental level.

Literature Review:

Quantum numbers are fundamental to understanding quantum mechanics. They describe the properties of electrons in atoms, such as their energy levels, orbital shapes, and magnetic orientation. Quantum numbers include:

1. *Principal Quantum Number (n):* Indicates the energy level of an electron.
2. *Azimuthal Quantum Number (l):* Describes the shape of the electron's orbital.
3. *Magnetic Quantum Number (m_l):* Specifies the orientation of the orbital in space.
4. *Spin Quantum Number (m_s):* Represents the intrinsic spin of the electron.

Historical Background

- *Bohr Model (1913):* Niels Bohr introduced the concept of quantized energy levels for electrons, which led to the formulation of the principal quantum number (n).
- *Schrödinger's Equation (1926):* Erwin Schrödinger developed a wave equation that describes how quantum states evolve over time, incorporating all quantum numbers.

Key Studies and Findings

1. **Pauli Exclusion Principle (1925):** *Wolfgang Pauli formulated the exclusion principle, which states that no two electrons in an atom can have the same set of quantum numbers. This principle was crucial in understanding electron configurations.*
2. **Quantum Number Determination:**
 - *Dirac's Equation (1928): Paul Dirac extended quantum theory to account for relativistic effects, leading to the inclusion of spin quantum numbers in the description of particles.*
 - *Hund's Rules (1927): Friedrich Hund developed rules to predict the electron configuration of atoms based on quantum numbers, particularly the arrangement of electrons to minimize energy.*

Modern Applications and Developments

1. **Quantum Computing:** *Recent advancements in quantum computing utilize principles of quantum mechanics, including quantum numbers, to develop new computational technologies.*
2. **Spectroscopy:** *The study of atomic spectra uses quantum numbers to analyze the energy levels and transitions of electrons in atoms, providing insights into atomic structure.*

Methodology:

[*Periodic Table with quantum number:*](#)

Group	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18											
Period																		Noble gases											
1	1 H																	2 He											
2	3 Li	4 Be											5 B	6 C	7 N	8 O	9 F	10 Ne											
3	11 Na	12 Mg											13 Al	14 Si	15 P	16 S	17 Cl	18 Ar											
4	19 K	20 Ca											21 Sc	22 Ti	23 V	24 Cr	25 Mn	26 Fe	27 Co	28 Ni	29 Cu	30 Zn	31 Ga	32 Ge	33 As	34 Se	35 Br	36 Kr	
5	37 Rb	38 Sr											39 Y	40 Zr	41 Nb	42 Mo	43 Tc	44 Ru	45 Rh	46 Pd	47 Ag	48 Cd	49 In	50 Sn	51 Sb	52 Te	53 I	54 Xe	
6	55 Cs	56 Ba	La to Yb											71 Lu	72 Hf	73 Ta	74 W	75 Re	76 Os	77 Ir	78 Pt	79 Au	80 Hg	81 Tl	82 Pb	83 Bi	84 Po	85 At	86 Rn
7	87 Fr	88 Ra	Ac to No											103 Lr	104 Rf	105 Db	106 Sg	107 Bh	108 Hs	109 Mt	110 Ds	111 Rg	112 Cn	113 Nh	114 Fl	115 Mc	116 Lv	117 Ts	118 Og
	s-block (incl. He)		f-block	d-block										p-block (excl. He)															
			Lanthanides	57 La	58 Ce	59 Pr	60 Nd	61 Pm	62 Sm	63 Eu	64 Gd	65 Tb	66 Dy	67 Ho	68 Er	69 Tm	70 Yb												
			Actinides	89 Ac	90 Th	91 Pa	92 U	93 Np	94 Pu	95 Am	96 Cm	97 Bk	98 Cf	99 Es	100 Fm	101 Md	102 No												

RED COLOR=NONMETALS,METALS

YELLOW COLOR=METALLOIDS

BLUE COLOR=TRANSITION METALS

GREEN COLOR=LANTHANIDES,ACTINIDES

112

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1

0

0

1/2, -1/2

U(2)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1

0

0

$1/2, +1/2$

U(3)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1

0

0

$-1/2, +1/2$

2

0

0

$-1/2, +1/2$

Re(4)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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B(5)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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C(6)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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N(7)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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O(8)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

F(9)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Ne(10)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Na(11)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Mg(12)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Al(13)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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Si(14)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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P(15)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

S(16)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Cl(17)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Ar(18)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

K(19)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ca(20)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Sc(21)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ti(22)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

V(23)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Cr(24)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Mn(25)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Fe(26)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Co(27)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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Ni(28)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
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4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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Cu(29)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Zn(30)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ga(31)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Ge(32)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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As(33)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
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4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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Se(34)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Br(35)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Kr(36)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Rb(37)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	0	0	1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	1/2,+1/2

Sr(38)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2

2	0	0	$-1/2, +1/2$
3	1	$-1, 0, +1$	$-1/2, +1/2$
3	2	$-2, -1, 0, +1, +2$	$-1/2, +1/2$
4	0	0	$-1/2, +1/2$
4	1	$-1, 0, +1$	$-1/2, +1/2$
5	0	0	$-1/2, +1/2$

Y(39)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	$-1/2, +1/2$
2	0	0	$-1/2, +1/2$
2	1	$-1, 0, +1$	$-1/2, +1/2$
3	0	0	$-1/2, +1/2$

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Zr(40)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Nb(41)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Mo(42)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Tc(43)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ru(44)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Rh(45)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Pd(46)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ag(47)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Cd(48)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

ln(49)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Sn(50)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Sb(51)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Te(52)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Xe(54)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Cs(55)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

6	0	0	1/2,+1/2
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Ba(56)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	----------

2	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	----------

3	0	0	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	----------

3	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	----------

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	----------

4	0	0	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	----------

4	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	----------

4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	----------

5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

La(57)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ce(58)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Pr(59)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Nd(60)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

6

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

Pm(61)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

2

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

2

1

-1,0,+1

-1/2,+1/2

3

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

3

1

-1,0,+1

-1/2,+1/2

3

2

-2,-1,0,+1,+2

-1/2,+1/2

4

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

4

1

-1,0,+1

-1/2,+1/2

4

2

-2,-1,0,+1,+2

-1/2,+1/2

4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Sm(62)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Eu(63)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Gd(64)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Tb(65)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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Dy(66)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	-----------

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	-----------

4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ho(67)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Er(68)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Tm(69)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Yb(70)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

6

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

Lu(71)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

2

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

2

1

-1,0,+1

-1/2,+1/2

3

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

3

1

-1,0,+1

-1/2,+1/2

3

2

-2,-1,0,+1,+2

-1/2,+1/2

4

0

0

-1/2,+1/2

4

1

-1,0,+1

-1/2,+1/2

4

2

-2,-1,0,+1,+2

-1/2,+1/2

4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Hf(72)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ta(73)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

W(74)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
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6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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Re(75)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
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4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
Os(76)			

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Ir(77)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Pt(78)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
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6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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Au(79)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Hg(80)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Tl(81)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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Pb(82)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	-----------

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	-----------

4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Bi(83)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Po(84)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
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At(85)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
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1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
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2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	-----------

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---	-----------

4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------	-----------

4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
---	---	---------------	-----------

4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Rn(86)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2

Fr(37)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	$1/2, +1/2$
2	0	0	$1/2, +1/2$
2	1	-1, 0, +1	$1/2, +1/2$
3	0	0	$1/2, +1/2$
3	1	-1, 0, +1	$1/2, +1/2$
3	2	-2, -1, 0, +1, +2	$1/2, +1/2$
4	0	0	$1/2, +1/2$
4	1	-1, 0, +1	$1/2, +1/2$
4	2	-2, -1, 0, +1, +2	$1/2, +1/2$
4	3	-3, -2, -1, 0, +1, +2, +3	$1/2, +1/2$
5	0	0	$1/2, +1/2$
5	1	-1, 0, +1	$1/2, +1/2$

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	1/2,+1/2

Ra(86)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	1/2,+1/2
5	3	0	1/2,+1/2
5	4	-1,0,+1	1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	1/2,+1/2

Ac(89)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Th(90)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Pa(91)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

U(92)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Np(93)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Pu(94)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Am(95)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Cm(96)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2

4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
Bk(97)			
Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)

1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2

6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Cf(98)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
Es(99)			
Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
Fm(100)			
Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2

4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
Md(101)			
Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

No(102)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Lr(103)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Rf(104)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
Db(105)			
Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Sg(106)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Bh(107)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Hs(108)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Mt(109)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

D_s(110)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
Rg(111)			
Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Cn(112)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

Nh(113)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
7	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Fl(114)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2

5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
7	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Mc(115)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2

2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2

7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
7	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Lv(116)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
7	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Ts(117)

Shell (n)

Subshell (l)

Orbital (m)

Spin (s)

1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2

6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
7	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Og(118)

Shell (n)	Subshell (l)	Orbital (m)	Spin (s)
1	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
2	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
3	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
3	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

3	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
4	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
4	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
4	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
5	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
5	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
5	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
5	3	-3,-2,-1,0,+1,+2,+3	-1/2,+1/2
6	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
6	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2
6	2	-2,-1,0,+1,+2	-1/2,+1/2
7	0	0	-1/2,+1/2
7	1	-1,0,+1	-1/2,+1/2

Result:

Quantum numbers are essential tools in understanding and describing the behavior of electrons within atoms and molecules in the framework of quantum mechanics. They serve several critical purposes in this context:

Electron Address System: Quantum numbers provide a systematic and unique way to identify and address individual electrons within an atom. Each electron is characterized by a set of quantum numbers, allowing us to differentiate between electrons in terms of their energy levels, subshells, orientations, and intrinsic properties.

Describing Electron Energy Levels: The principal quantum number (n) indicates the main energy level or shell in which an electron resides. Different energy levels have different allowed subshells and orbitals, forming the basis for understanding electron distribution and organization within an atom.

Determining Orbital Shapes and Orientations: The azimuthal quantum number (ℓ) and the magnetic quantum number (m_ℓ) collectively define the shape and orientation of electron orbitals within subshells. This information is crucial for understanding the spatial distribution of electron density around the nucleus.

Incorporating Electron Spin: The spin quantum number (m_s) accounts for the intrinsic angular momentum, or "spin," of electrons. This property gives rise to magnetic behavior and contributes to the overall magnetic properties of atoms and molecules.

Explaining Chemical Bonding: Quantum numbers play a vital role in explaining the principles of chemical bonding. The arrangement of electrons in orbitals determines the reactivity and chemical properties of elements. Quantum numbers help elucidate why certain atoms bond with others to form molecules, and why some molecules exhibit distinct shapes and properties.

Understanding Spectroscopy: Quantum numbers are crucial in interpreting spectroscopic data. Transitions between energy levels are governed by changes in quantum numbers,

and these transitions produce spectral lines with characteristic frequencies. Analyzing these transitions allows scientists to identify elements and understand their electronic structures.

Predicting and Explaining Periodic Trends: The arrangement of electrons in atoms, determined by quantum numbers, underlies the periodic properties of elements. Periodic trends such as atomic size, ionization energy, and electron affinity are directly related to the electronic configuration of atoms.

Basis for Quantum Mechanical Calculations: Quantum numbers provide the foundation for quantum mechanical calculations, allowing scientists to predict and simulate atomic and molecular behavior. These calculations are used in fields ranging from material science to drug discovery.

In essence, quantum numbers provide a structured framework for describing the complex behavior of electrons within atoms and molecules. They facilitate our ability to comprehend and predict the properties of matter at the atomic and molecular scales, bridging the gap between classical physics and the intricate world of quantum mechanics

Discussion:

Wave-Particle Duality: Quantum mechanics introduces the concept of wave-particle duality, where particles like electrons exhibit both particle-like and wave-like behavior. This duality is described by the Schrödinger equation, a fundamental equation in quantum mechanics.

Quantization of Energy Levels: Quantum mechanics dictates that energy levels in atoms and molecules are quantized, meaning they can only take on certain discrete values. This quantization is described by the principal quantum number (n), where higher values of n correspond to higher energy levels.

Orbital Shapes and Subshells: Electrons occupy specific regions around the nucleus called orbitals. Each orbital has a distinct shape, which is determined by the azimuthal quantum number (ℓ). The ℓ value also corresponds to subshells, such as s, p, d, and f orbitals.

Spatial Orientation of Orbitals: The magnetic quantum number (m_ℓ) specifies the spatial orientation of an orbital within a subshell. For example, in a p subshell, there are three orbitals oriented along the x, y, and z axes, each represented by a different m_ℓ value.

Electron Spin: Electrons possess an intrinsic property called spin, which contributes to their angular momentum and magnetic behavior. The spin quantum number (m_s) distinguishes between two possible spin states: $+\frac{1}{2}$ (spin-up) and $-\frac{1}{2}$ (spin-down).

Pauli Exclusion Principle: The Pauli Exclusion Principle states that no two electrons in an atom can have the same set of quantum numbers. This principle is essential for explaining the arrangement of electrons in orbitals and the stability of matter.

Aufbau Principle: The Aufbau Principle outlines the process of filling electron orbitals in ascending order of energy. Electrons fill lower-energy orbitals before higher-energy ones, following the sequence of subshells dictated by the azimuthal quantum number.

Hund's Rule: Hund's Rule states that electrons will occupy degenerate orbitals (orbitals with the same energy) singly before pairing up. This leads to the maximum electron spin alignment, minimizing electron-electron repulsion.

Quantum Mechanical Calculations: Quantum numbers are used in solving the Schrödinger equation to predict the energy levels and probabilities of finding electrons in various quantum states. These calculations are essential for understanding atomic and molecular properties.

Periodic Table and Trends: Quantum numbers provide the basis for the arrangement of elements in the periodic table. Elements within the same group often have similar electron configurations, leading to predictable trends in their properties.

Conclusion:

Quantum number is vastly used all over the quantum sector. Principle quantum number is used to define the energy level of the electron. Azimuth quantum number is used to define subshell state of position like, s, p, d, f . Magnetic quantum number is used to define angular momentum orientation with subshells, and spin quantum number is used to define electron spinning direction up or down. This is quantum number and how we can use it with various sectors in quantum mechanics.

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